

**Expeditious analysis of combined antiretroviral tablets by
chemometric assisted UV spectroscopic methods**

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Abstract:

Application of chemometric models to the UV spectral data has become efficient, popular and facilitates the easy analysis of multicomponent formulations. In the current study, Chemometric assisted UV spectroscopic methods namely principal component regression (PCR) and partial least squares regression (PLS) were employed for the analysis of prominent antiretroviral fixed dose combination comprising of Lamivudine (LMV), Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (TDF) and Dolutegravir Sodium (DTS) which was found to be very effective in reducing the mortality rate of HIV infected patients. PCR and PLS methods were executed for the calibration and validation sets which consists of twelve and seven standard mixture solutions respectively in the concentration ranges of 5-25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of LMV, 5-30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of TDF and 3-18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of DTS. Data modelling was done in the wavelength range of 220 nm -370 nm with 2 nm data interval at the chosen optimal number of factors. The results obtained from both the models depicted their validity and can be applied for the expeditious analysis of LMV, TDF and TDS in their commercial formulation.

Key words: Chemometric models, Principal component regression, Partial least squares regression, antiretroviral fixed dose combination.

Introduction:

One of the biggest threats to global public health is HIV, the virus that causes AIDS. However, there is a global commitment to halting the spread of HIV and guaranteeing that all HIV-positive individuals have access to treatment¹. The combination antiretroviral regimens were found to be very effective in reducing the mortality rate of HIV infected patients². The study presented here is done on the combination of an integrase strand transfer inhibitor (Dolutegravir) and two nucleoside reverse

transcriptase inhibitors (Lamivudine and Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate). The selected combination is available in the tablet dosage form and indexed by WHO as one of the first line treatment for AIDS patients.

Upon the literature survey, it was revealed that few analytical methods were reported for the determination of Lamivudine (LMV), Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (TDF) and Dolutegravir Sodium (DTS) that employs the Chromatographic techniques which are based on more time consumption, requiring a greater number of samples and solvents³⁻¹⁶. There is no reported UV spectroscopic method for simultaneous estimation of LMV, TDF and DTS in pharmaceutical dosage form in the literature to best of our knowledge. The analytical methods that are based on ultraviolet-visible spectroscopic techniques are among the most widely employed due to their experimental simplicity and rapidity. However, the usage of traditional or conventional ultraviolet methods for the simultaneous determination of these drugs is difficult because of the overlapping absorption spectra of the drugs in a bright region and the interferences of drugs with each other make unsuitable for exact quantitative assessment¹⁷⁻²². Hence, efforts were made to develop simple, fast, accurate and precise UV spectroscopic methods by the application of chemometric models for the determination of LMV, TDF and DTS in their combined dosage form.

Experimental

Materials & Instruments:

The pharmaceutical grade samples of Lamivudine, Tenofovir and Dolutegravir were obtained as gift samples from Giyaan Pharmaceuticals Pvt Ltd., Tirupati, India. Fixed dose combination containing 50 mg DTS, 300 mg TDF and 300 mg LMV was purchased from local market. Acetonitrile was used as solvent in the present study.

Weighing of samples was carried out by using Shimadzu electronic balance (AY 220). Shimadzu UV-1800 spectrophotometer equipped with UV Probe software was used for the spectroscopic measurements and data acquisition. The software Unscrambler X (Camo analytics) was used for the execution of the chemometric models. Regression and statistical analysis were carried out by using Microsoft excel 2013.

Methods:

Chemometric assisted UV spectrophotometric methods like Principal component regression (PCR) and Partial least squares regression (PLS) were developed and validated in the current study. Acetonitrile was chosen as the solvent for the three drugs LMV, TDF & DTS as they showed good solubility. Suitable concentrations of LMV, TDF & DTS were prepared in Acetonitrile and their UV spectra were recorded in the range of 200-400 nm. The absorption maxima of LMV, TDF & DTS were found to be 272 nm, 260 nm and 263 nm respectively. Calibration curves of LMV, TDF & DTS were established in the concentration ranges of 5-25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 5-30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 3-18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ respectively. Assay sample solution was prepared from the combined tablet dosage form in order to get a concentration of 18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ & 3 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of LMV, TDF & DTS respectively.

Execution of PCR & PLS models:

An experimental design was generated for the drugs in their calibration curve ranges. According to the design, standard mixture solutions containing different ratios of LMV, TDF & DTS were prepared and scanned in UV-VIS spectrophotometer in the wavelength range of 200-400 nm using Acetonitrile as blank. The recorded spectral data of the standard mixture solutions was transferred into MS- EXCEL. The entire

data comprising of absorbances, concentrations of the drugs in the mixture solutions and wavelengths were arranged into columns and rows thus forming a huge matrix. The matrix sheet of the data in the wavelength range of 220-370 nm with 2 nm data interval was imported into the UNSCRAMBLER X version 10.5 software (Camo analytics). Two sets, calibration set and validation set were created for the construction of calibration and for the prediction of concentrations in standard mixture solutions respectively (Table 1). Further computations were carried by applying PCR and PLS models to predict the concentrations in the combined dosage form.

Table 1: Calibration and validation set for PCR and PLS methods

Calibration set ^a				Validation set ^a			
Mixture	LAM	TDF	DTS	Mixture	LAM	TDF	DTS
1	20	10	9	11	10	20	12
2	25	15	15	12	20	5	15
3	25	20	6	13	15	30	18
4	25	30	9	14	20	20	18
5	25	25	18	15	15	25	9
6	20	15	12	16	5	10	3
7	20	30	3	17	5	20	12
8	20	25	6				
9	5	5	9				
10	10	15	3				
11	10	10	15				
12	5	30	12				

^aConcentration values are expressed as $\mu\text{g/mL}$

Results and discussion:

UV spectroscopic method development for the analysis of LMV, TDF & DTS yielded good correlation coefficient values which was carried out in the concentration ranges of 5-25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 5-30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 3-18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ respectively as

shown in Fig no 1. Severe overlapping of the absorption spectra of the three drugs was observed which was depicted in Fig no 2 and this was resolved by the application of chemometric models, Principal component regression (PCR) and Partial least squares regression (PLS).

Fig. 1. Overlay absorption spectra of LMV, TDF & DTS

Fig. 2: Calibration and linearity curves of LMV, TDF & DTS

Application of Chemometric PLS and PCR models:

Selection of factors (principal components and latent variables) and wavelength range plays pivotal role in the chemometric models. In order to enhance the quality of the study, the wavelength range of 220-370 nm with 2 nm data interval was chosen as the region below 220 nm showed more noise and the region above 370 nm depicted very minimal absorbance values. The calibration data set of twelve standard mixture solutions was subjected to a K-fold process cross-validation approach in order to determine the ideal number of Principal components (PCs) and latent variables (LVs)

for the PCR and PLS models, respectively. The predicted and actual concentrations were compared and the errors were identified using the Root mean square error of cross validation (RMSECV) values. RMSECV, an indicative parameter of accuracy and precision should be as low as possible and these values were calculated at each given no. of PCs and LVs in PCR and PLS respectively. The optimum number of PCs and LVs with least RMSECV values as shown in Fig no.3 was chosen for the execution of chemometric models. The calibration set at the chosen PCs in PCR and LVs in PLS was optimized as all the statistical parameters like mean, standard deviation (SD), correlation coefficient (R^2), Root mean square error of calibration (RMSEC) were found to be in the limits as depicted in Tables 2 & 3.

Fig. 3: RMSECV graph for PCR & PLS models.

Table 2: Calibration data set results obtained by PCR method

Calibration mixture	Principal Component Regression [PCR]					
	Predicted values ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)			% Recovery		
	LMV	TDF	DTS	LMV	TDF	DTS
1.	19.868	10.247	9.156	99.339	102.474	101.734
2.	25.106	15.113	15.012	100.425	100.757	100.082
3.	25.108	19.983	5.865	100.434	99.917	97.744
4.	25.015	30.049	9.030	100.060	100.162	100.336
5.	25.008	25.003	17.994	100.033	100.012	99.969
6.	19.737	14.719	11.838	98.683	98.124	98.654

7.	19.907	29.544	3.100	99.533	98.479	103.326
8.	20.131	25.369	6.030	100.656	101.478	100.496
9.	5.068	5.074	8.990	101.356	101.471	99.890
10.	10.016	15.041	2.947	100.159	100.276	98.221
11.	10.072	9.702	15.071	100.722	97.018	100.476
12.	4.964	30.156	11.966	99.277	100.519	99.720
MEAN				100.057	100.057	100.054
SD				0.742	1.541	1.501
%RSD				0.742	1.540	1.500
Coefficient of correlation (R^2)				0.111	0.227	0.087
RMSEC				0.9997	0.9992	0.9996
RMSECV				0.285	0.595	0.321

Table 3: Calibration data set results obtained by PLS method

Calibration mixture	Partial least squares regression [PLS]					
	Predicted values ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)			% Recovery		
	LMV	TDF	DTS	LMV	TDF	DTS
1.	19.951	10.271	9.044	99.753	102.711	100.484
2.	25.123	15.013	15.012	100.491	100.083	100.082
3.	25.191	20.096	15.038	100.765	100.480	100.251
4.	24.941	29.832	5.931	99.764	99.439	98.852
5.	25.006	24.969	8.936	100.024	99.877	99.291
6.	19.707	14.773	18.004	98.536	98.486	100.025
7.	19.949	29.523	11.926	99.744	98.409	99.387
8.	20.026	25.570	3.068	100.132	102.282	102.250
9.	5.035	4.833	6.073	100.705	96.670	101.215
10.	10.001	15.008	8.976	100.009	100.057	99.735
11.	10.025	9.947	2.979	100.250	99.475	99.308
12.	5.045	30.164	15.047	100.891	100.546	100.314
MEAN				100.089	99.876	100.077
SD				0.634	1.636	0.936
%RSD				0.634	1.638	0.936
Coefficient of correlation (R^2)				0.112	0.254	0.051
RMSEC				0.9997	0.9990	0.9998
RMSECV				0.308	0.593	0.235

Validation and assay of Chemometric PLS and PCR models:

Further, calibration set was applied to the validation set comprising of seven standard mixture solutions to determine its predictive ability. The test set results demonstrated the developed model's correctness and Root mean square error of prediction (RMSEP) values of both PCR and PLS models were found to be extremely low, indicating high accuracy. The validation set's percent recovery, RMSEP, and correlation coefficient data (Tables 4 & 5) showed how well the PCR and PLS models could predict the quantities in the commercial formulation. Optimized and validated PCR and PLS models were used to determine the concentrations of LMV, TDF and DTS in the sample solution and the assay results were shown in Table 6 respectively. The analysis results meet the acceptance criteria, indicating that both PCR and PLS models can be applied for simultaneous determination of drugs without previous separation. The Statistical parameters obtained from PCR and PLS models for calibration set, validation set and sample solution were compiled and presented in Tables 7.

Table 4: Validation data set results obtained by PCR method

Validation mixture	Principal Component Regression [PCR]					
	Predicted values ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)			% Recovery		
	LMV	TDF	DTS	LMV	TDF	DTS
13.	10.661	18.777	11.168	106.608	93.885	93.063
14.	19.276	4.484	15.674	96.382	89.687	104.492
15.	14.681	29.935	16.999	97.874	99.783	94.441
16.	19.589	19.604	17.326	97.943	98.021	96.254
17.	15.278	24.807	9.635	101.850	99.229	107.051
18.	4.824	9.580	2.848	96.477	95.796	94.937
19.	4.917	20.561	12.264	98.347	102.807	102.198
	MEAN			99.354	97.030	98.919
	SD			3.678	4.323	5.556
	%RSD			3.702	4.455	5.617
	RMSEP			0.470	0.802	0.557

Table 5: Validation data set results obtained by PLS method

Validation mixture	Partial least squares regression [PLS]					
	Predicted values ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)			% Recovery		
	LMV	TDF	DTS	LMV	TDF	DTS
13.	10.778	18.646	11.045	107.777	93.228	92.044
14.	19.226	4.587	15.674	96.130	91.745	104.494
15.	14.832	30.133	17.055	98.881	100.442	94.748
16.	19.634	19.871	17.347	98.169	99.357	96.371
17.	15.275	24.866	9.623	101.835	99.466	106.927
18.	4.794	9.342	2.821	95.872	93.417	94.020
19.	4.977	20.627	12.248	99.537	103.137	102.065
MEAN				99.743	97.256	98.667
SD				4.087	4.385	5.771
%RSD				4.097	4.509	5.849
RMSEP				0.372	0.742	0.582

Table 6: Assay results obtained by PCR & PLS methods

Sample (Commercial formulation)			
Chemometric models	Drugs	Predicted value ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Assay (w/w)
PCR	LMV	17.615	97.859
	TDF	18.730	104.055
	DTS	2.868	95.613
PLS	LMV	17.842	99.124
	TDF	19.314	107.300
	DTS	2.818	93.940

Table 7: Compiled statistical parameters of PCR & PLS methods

Statistical parameters	PCR			PLS		
	LMV	TDF	DTS	LMV	TDF	DTS
Concentration range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	5-25	5-30	3-18	5-25	5-30	3-18
No. of factors	7	7	7	7	7	7
R^2	0.9997	0.9992	0.9996	0.9997	0.9990	0.9998
RMSEC	0.111	0.227	0.087	0.112	0.254	0.051
RMSECV	0.285	0.595	0.321	0.308	0.593	0.235
RMSEP	0.470	0.802	0.557	0.372	0.742	0.582
Assay	97.859	104.055	95.613	99.124	107.300	93.940

Conclusion:

Analysts are usually interested in analytical methods that have good accuracy and precision and can analyze multicomponent formulations in a short amount of time. This is possible when chemometric instruments are used in conjunction with analytical techniques. Chemometrics is a useful tool that supports spectroscopic techniques, enabling them to determine pharmaceuticals in multicomponent formulations simultaneously with great power and efficiency. Such expeditious chemometric assisted UV spectroscopic methods like, Principal component regression and Partial least squares regression were developed for the analysis of one of the most prominent anti-retroviral regimens comprising of Lamivudine, Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate and Dolutegravir Sodium. The results of the developed models demonstrated the ability of chemometric tools for easier, quick and efficient drug quantification and they can be successfully applied in the regular analysis of pharmaceuticals in quality control laboratories.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Smt. P. Sulochana, chairperson and Sri.P. Praneeth, director of Sri Padmavathi School of Pharmacy, Tiruchanoor, AP, India for providing necessary infrastructure and facilities to carry out this research work.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

References

1. Global Statistics. HIV.gov. Available from: <https://www.hiv.gov/hiv-basics/overview/data-and-trends/global-statistics>

2. Collaboration HC. The effect of combined antiretroviral therapy on the overall mortality of HIV-infected individuals. *AIDS*. 2009 Nov 28;24(1):123–37. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1097/qad.0b013e3283324283>
3. Nekkala K, Shanmukha Kumar J V, Ramachandran D. Analytical method development and validation for the simultaneous estimation of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir drug product by reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography method. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research* [Internet]. 2018 Feb 1;11(2):164. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.22159/ajpcr.2018.v11i2.22465>
4. Jagadabi V, Kumar PVN, Pamidi S, Ramaprasad LA, Nagaraju D. A stability-indicating hplc method for the determination of potential impurities in a new fixed dose combination of dolutegravir, lamivudine and tenofovir disoproxil fumarate tablets used in the first line treatment of hiv-1 infection. *International Research Journal of Pharmacy* [Internet]. 2018 Jun 22;9(5):65–74. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.7897/2230-8407.09575>
5. MastanammaMSk, Jyothi JA, Saidulu SP, Varalakshmi VM. Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for the Simultaneous Estimation of Lamivudine, Tenofovir Alafenamide and Dolutegravir Bulk and their Combined Dosage Form. *Pharmaceutical Methods* [Internet]. 2018 Aug 7;9(2):49–55. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5530/phm.2018.2.10>
6. Kalpana T, Raja Rajeswari T, Ganji RR. Development and validation of analytical method for determination of dolutegravir sodium, lamivudine and tenofovir disoproxil fumarate using reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography [Internet]. Vols. 9–8, *Der Pharma Chemica*. 2017 p. 117–27. Available from: <http://www.derpharmachemica.com/archive.html>

7. Goud M, Avanapu SR, Suddala R, Joginpally B.R. Pharmacy College, Bhaskar Pharmacy College, University of the Cumberland. Method development and validation for simultaneous determination of lamivudine and tenofovir in tablet dosage form by RP- HPLC [Internet]. Vols. 5–Suppl 3, International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences. 2013 Jun p. 215–8. Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260787113>
8. Kasula P et al, Kumar N V, Reddy A, G S, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Sri Padmavathi School of Pharmacy, Tiruchanoor, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh, India. Six spectroscopic methods for simultaneous estimation of lamivudine and tenofovir in tablets. Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research. 2018 Jan;10:203–11.
9. Bindu NMH, Gowthami NB. Utilization of lipids, polymers by modern techniques for innovative pharmaceutical formulations and medical devices. International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technology [Internet]. 2020 Sep 11;2(1):07–11. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.33974/ijrpst.v2i1.223>
10. M V, N SJ. Development of Validation and Stability Indicating Method of Anti-HIV Dolutegravir Drug and its Related Impurities by Using RP-HPLC. Journal of Chromatography and Separation Techniques [Internet]. 2020 Jan 1;11(1). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.35248/2157-7064.20.11.426>
11. Godela R, G S. An effective stability indicating RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Dolutegravir and Lamivudine in bulk and their tablet dosage form. Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences [Internet]. 2020 Apr 15;6(1). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43094-020-00026-0>
12. Rao NM, Sankar DG. Development and validation of stability-indicating HPLC method for simultaneous determination of Lamivudine, Tenofovir, and Dolutegravir in bulk and their tablet dosage form. Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences

- [Internet]. 2015 Dec 1;1(2):73–7. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fjps.2015.11.002>
13. Noorbasha K, Nurbasha S. A new validated stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for simultaneous quantification of dolutegravir and lamivudine in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* [Internet]. 2020 Jul 28;6(1). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43094-020-00060-y>
 14. Sireesha D. Analytical method development and validation for the simultaneous estimation of lamivudine and tenofovir disoproxil fumarate by RP-HPLC Method. *MOJ Proteomics & Bioinformatics* [Internet]. 2016 Nov 30;4(5). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.15406/mojpb.2016.04.00134>
 15. Pal N, Rao AS, Ravikumar P. Simultaneous HPLC Method Development and Validation for Estimation of Lamivudine, Abacavir and Dolutegravir in Combined Dosage Form with their Stability Studies. *Asian Journal of Chemistry* [Internet]. 2015 Nov 13;28(2):273–6. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.14233/ajchem.2016.19116>
 16. Bhavar GB. High-Performance liquid chromatographic and High-Performance Thin-Layer chromatographic method for quantitative estimation of dolutegravir sodium in bulk drug and pharmaceutical dosage form. *Scientia Pharmaceutica* [Internet]. 2016 Jan 1;84(2):305–20. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3797/scipharm.1507-09>
 17. Archakam SC, Palur K, Galla R, Padiri SS, Tulasi PK, Diviti R. Simultaneous determination of amitriptyline hydrochloride and propranolol hydrochloride in commercial formulation by multitudinal UV and multivariate FT-IR spectroscopic methods. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research* [Internet]. 2024 May 28;58(2s):s552–7. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5530/ijper.58.2s.57>
 18. Palur K, Archakam SC, Koganti B. Development and validation of chemometric assisted UV methods for the simultaneous determination of ambroxol hydrochloride,

- terbutaline sulphate and guaiphenesin in pharmaceutical dosage form. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research* [Internet]. 2023 Jan 9;57(1):242–9. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5530/001954641128>
19. Palur K, Archakam SC, Koganti B. Chemometric assisted UV spectrophotometric and RP-HPLC methods for simultaneous determination of paracetamol, diphenhydramine, caffeine and phenylephrine in tablet dosage form. *Spectrochimica Acta Part a Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy* [Internet]. 2020 Aug 8;243:118801. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2020.118801>
20. Palur K, Koganti B, Archakam S. Chemometric-assisted RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous determination of ambroxol hydrochloride, terbutaline sulfate, and guaiphenesin in combined dosage form. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science* [Internet]. 2019 Sep 1;9(9):92–7. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.7324/japs.2019.90913>
21. Palur NK, Bharathi Koganti N, Archakam NSC. Development and validation of chemometric assisted analytical methods for simultaneous estimation of Atorvastatin calcium and Aspirin in capsule dosage form. *International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences* [Internet]. 2019 Jul 6;10(3):1692–7. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.26452/ijrps.v10i3.1342>
22. Palur K, Koganti B, Archakam SC, Chenchugari S, Nagireddy B, Devabhaktuni MB, et al. Simultaneous estimation of atorvastatin and aspirin in bulk and capsule dosage form by chemometric assisted spectrophotometric methods. *Journal of Young Pharmacists* [Internet]. 2016 Aug 1;8(4):424–9. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5530/jyp.2016.4.19>